

BACTERICERA SP. ON CARROT FIELDS: RESULTS PREVIEW

M.J. ZANÓN*, G. VÁZQUEZ, M.C. GARCÍA, L. GUTIÉRREZ

CERTIS EUROPE B.V. SEVERO OCHOA 18, 03203 ELCHE, SPAIN.

***Corresponding author: zanon@certiseurope.com.**

Three integrated pest management programs were designed in two trials conducted on carrot crops placed in Villena (Alicante, Spain). Different biopesticides have been included according to previous results showing different effects on eggs, larvae and adults of *Bactericera trigonica* considered the main vector of *Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum* (CaLsol) affecting carrots. A complete randomized block design was used with 4 replications (70 m² per replicate); carrot variety Soprano was used and seeds were previously analysed with negative results to the presence of CaLsol. Trial protocols included untreated control, straight applications of paraffin oil (54.6% EW at 1% v/v) and three different programs applying alternatively treatments with maltodextrin (59.8% SL at 25L/ha), *Beauveria bassiana* (10.7% OD at 1L/ha), natural pyrethrins (4% EC at 0.75L/ha), acetamiprid (20% SP at 50g/hl) and paraffin oil. First applications were scheduled in alignment with the first captures detected in yellow sticky traps placed in both experimental areas. Treatments and evaluations will cover the crop cycle. Number of larvae and eggs in 100 leaves per replicate are being determined weekly in order to quantify the efficacy of each treatment. At the end of the trials, total production will be evaluated taking 20 plants per each replicate. Trials and evaluations are still being done, with the first treatments applied in August 2018 and the finalization of the crop expected for November 2018. Although the incidence in the untreated check is still low in both trials (maximum detected 1.53 and 2.1 larvae per leaf and 1.53 and 0.35 eggs per leaf, respectively), first results shown a slightly decrease of insect incidence after applying the designed programs when compared with straight applications of paraffin oil. Program development including the available active ingredients to control the levels of the vector population and working in a sustainable frame, will be the key target helping to fight against the disease dissemination in the field.